

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE ETHNIC GROUP AFFILIATION AND L2 PROFICIENCY LINK: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE

Lina Farsia
Universitas Muhammadiyah Aceh
lina.farsia@unmuha.ac.id

Abstract

There are many factors affecting in a second language (L2) Proficiency. In this literature review, one of the factors that was examined is the ethnic group affiliation. Ethnic group affiliation and L2 proficiency" refers to the relationship between a person's ethnicity and their proficiency in L2. Research has shown that ethnic group affiliation can have an impact on language learning and proficiency, with some ethnic groups performing better or worse than others in learning a second language. Research in this area has important implications for language education policies and programs, as well as for understanding the complex ways in which ethnicity, culture, and language learning intersect.

Keyword : Ethnic Group, L2 Proficiency,

INTRODUCTION

There are many factors that can influence the relationship between ethnic group affiliation and L2 proficiency, including socio-cultural background, family support, educational opportunities, and motivation. For example, individuals who come from a bilingual or multilingual family background may have an advantage in learning a second language, while individuals who do not have access to formal language education may struggle to achieve high levels of proficiency.

Other factors that can impact the relationship between ethnic group affiliation and L2 proficiency include the type of language being learned, the age at which the individual begins learning the language, and the individual's exposure to the language outside of formal instruction. For example, individuals who begin learning a second language at a younger age may have an advantage over those who start later in life, while those who have access to opportunities for immersion in the language